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RECORDS MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND PRODUCTIVITY OF ACADEMIC HEADS OF DEPARTMENT IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper examined records management practices and productivity of academic Heads of Department in public Universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study adopted correlational design. The population of the study comprised 400 academic Heads of Department in four public Universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A sample of 120 respondents was drawn through simple random sampling techniques. Two research instruments titled 'Records Management Practices Questionnaire' (RMPQ) and 'Academic Heads of Department Questionnaire' (AHDQ) were used for data collection. Content validity of the instruments was ensured by test experts and reliability consistency of the instruments was 0.67 and 0.65 using Cronbach's alpha. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyse data collected via Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22.0. The findings of the hypotheses 1 and 2 showed that: a significant relationship existed between monitoring of staff records and productivity of academic Heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria ($r = .631$; $N=120$; $p<0.05$); and a significant relationship existed between controlling of student records and productivity of academic Heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria ($r = .675$; $N=120$; $p<0.05$). Based on the findings, the study concluded that monitoring and controlling of statutory records enhanced the productivity of academic Heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State. Therefore, it is recommended amongst other that university management should direct all academic Heads of Department to monitor and control statutory records of staff and students in tertiary institutions for better service delivery in teaching, research and community service.

Keywords: Records, Management, Practices and Service Delivery

Introduction

University is the ivory tower where teaching, research and community service take place for attaining academic excellence. The term 'record' derived its origin from the Latin word "recordari" meaning to be mindful of, or to remember (Abdulrahman, 2015). It refers to

recorded information, regardless of form or medium, received and maintained by an agency, institution, organization or an individual. University record practices could either be manual or electronic depending on the administrative strategies employed by the management. According to Akinwumiju and Agabi (2008), they include statutory and non-statutory records. Statutory records according to Adebayo, (2014) are those records required by law to be kept as a matter of routine to help in the administration of the school. The non-statutory records are those records that a school manager may consider vital for the day to day management of the school but are not required by law to be kept by the school. However, A number of reasons could be responsible for this challenge. Recordpoint (2018) states the common challenges facing records management which includes information overload, lack of resources, lack of awareness, keeping everything is not the best policy. other are decentralization, facing today, preparing for tomorrow, maturity and expense.

More so, University may choose to maintain its records centrally, decentralized, or in a mixed fashion. This presupposed that Heads of Departments at universities should be in charge of taking good care of the records they produce. This is crucial since keeping track of records and arranging them makes it easier to locate information and records when needed. Management records practices could be kept manually or electronically. Manual records waste a lot of time, finance and manpower which affect tertiary institutions administration in the area of storage, preservation and records of accurate information to facilitate the teaching and learning process. School records are kept under lock and key or electronically by the administrators in the system. According to Ujah (2016) a good record contains all relevant details which are recorded or written accurately and honestly. However, Hanior (2016) posited that the person responsible for filling them should ensure that all the columns are accurately completed. It has been observed that administration of manual records keeping in Nigerian tertiary institutions bedeviled with inexperience personnel, lack of fund to procure facilities like computer, internet, electricity supply poor administration of records about the teachers and students can hinder the success of the whole system. electronic records keeping become an issue of great concerned to all stakeholders in tertiary institution that include: Government, TETFund Manager, educational administrator and non-governmental organization parents, lecturers, student, Electronic records are computerized and automated version of the manual record keeping. It is a modern record keeping through the use of Information Communication Technology (ICT) gadgets. Thus, ICT is a major tool for managing and transforming educational sector with good administration. It involves uses of software package for processing of students' registration, admission letter, result checking, curriculum design, time-table, staff and student attendance, scheme of work, course materials, newsletter and media dissemination, payment of school fees, staff recruitment, log book and so on. Such records are kept by the Registrar, Dean, Head of Department and Administrative staff. The relevance of these school records according to Ujah (2016) is they serve as a bank where vital and crucial information concerning both students and the school are deposited for future reference and retrieval. Therefore, institutions dealing with man and his activities need records to discharge their duties efficiently. More so, productivity is the overall efficacy and efficiency of completing tasks. The standard by which Heads of Department productivity in Nigerian public universities is frequently judged on the structure and capacity of Departmental Staff and students, the amount of research conducted and directed by the staff in the institutions, and the amount of community service the staff performs.

Statement of the Problem

Recently, there were poor monitoring, control and maintenance of record management practice that formed part of the challenges. It has been observed that some Heads of Department in Nigerian public universities do not take record management seriously and most of their statutory records are stored on papers stocked in files, which were packed inside drawers, lockers, cabinets, book shelves and boxes which are not properly secured. The record management practice adopted exposed important school records to destruction by pests, termites, cockroaches, rodents, rainfall, flooding, pilfering, fire outbreaks and eventual loss. In the 21st century, it is expected that record management practice in universities system should be done electronically using computers and cloud storage. But unfortunately, it is perceived that most public university Heads of department in Lagos State, Nigeria seem not to adopt information management system, which involves the use of cloud storage, flash drive, memory cards, CD Roms, flash drives, audio recorders, and other information management devices for proper record keeping to improve on their administrative tasks.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was to:

1. examine the relationship between monitoring of staff records and productivity of academic Heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.
2. determine examine the relationship between controlling of student records and productivity of academic Heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

Based on the research questions, the following hypotheses were tested:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between monitoring of staff records and productivity of academic Heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between controlling of student records and productivity of academic Heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

A records management practice seems to be a framework that provides significant managerial planning, organising, monitoring and control over the statutory and non-statutory records in school organization. Khumalo and Chigariro (2017) argue that records management program provides a primary means of creating and disseminating knowledge, training, and tools about best practices in creating and managing all types of institutional records. Because a university's activities are documented in the records it creates, records management is vital to the smooth operation of higher education institutions like universities. These documents are an essential resource for ensuring that the institution is managed successfully and efficiently and is answerable to its staff, students, and the community it serves. Records assist in decision-making, give evidence of policies, decisions, transactions, and operations, document general operational activities, and support the institution in legal proceedings. Record keeping is vital to the university system as it generates its information and experiences influx of information and an outflow of the same to the society which demands transparency and accountability. In the words of Ibara (2010), without records, there can be no accountability. However, Dale and Cory (2021) defined a record keeping device as any type of computing hardware that is used for storing, porting or

extracting data files and objects. Record keeping practice can hold and store information both temporarily and permanently. Garry and Dave (2021), viewed record keeping as collective methods and technologies that capture and retain digital information on electromagnetic, optical or silicon-based record keeping media. There are two different types of record keeping devices namely the primary record keeping device and the secondary record keeping device. The primary record keeping devices are generally smaller in size; designed to hold data temporarily and are internal to the computer. They have the fastest data access speed, and these types of devices include RAM and cache memory (Dale & Cory, 2021). The Secondary record keeping devices usually have larger record keeping capacity, and they store data permanently. These types of devices include the hard disk, the optical disk drive and USB record keeping device (Ryan, Ian, Tracy-Lee, & Mohana, 2020).

Perhaps, it is crucial for all university administrator to assume accountability for the correct upkeep and management of their archives. The keeping of school records was enshrined in the Public Education Edict of 1974. The edict stipulated that at every public or private institution, records and books shall be kept by the person in charge and produced at the request of an inspecting officer or manager (Koko & Nwiyi, 2019). Under the education law, there are two types of school records that a school is authorized to keep. These are statutory and non-statutory school records. Statutory school records are those records that are mandatory under education law to be kept by each school viz: admission register, class attendance register, syllabus, lesson note, scheme of work, diary, time table, visitors' book, log book, staff record book, corporal punishment book and so on (Gede, 2011). Moreover, university administrator does not need to keep large files in a large room and consume more paper. What the administrator needs is to integrate technology into the school system and work smart and not necessarily hard as the technology permits access to files every time they need them even when they are not in the school premises (Falana, 2018). On the other hand, non-statutory school records are those records not required by law to be kept, but are kept because they provide useful source of information not only for members of the school community but for people outside the school system as pointed out by (Peretomode, 2000). Records practices can be categorized into two: Statutory Academic Records and Non-Statutory Academic Records.

1. Statutory Academic Records: These records are required by law for academic and administrative routine of the tertiary institutions such as students Admission/withdrawals register; curriculum, syllabus/academic prospectus, module/semester course work; academic time table; academic calendar, logbook; visitor's book; staff movement book; certificate book, visitors book; school diary; marking guide, online course registration, online lecture note, examination record sheet; academic profile/cumulative records, conference proceeding record, seminar record, query book, education edicts and regulation; National policy on Education booklet and so on.

2. Non-statutory Academic Records: These records are not required by law but necessary for smooth administration of tertiary institutions such as administrative records; cash book; stock book; school calendar; inventory book; staff minute book; school magazine; inspection or supervision report file; Confidential report forms; requisition book; records of physical development; duty roster book; year book; hand book; inventory book; health record book and fees register; year book, punishment book, disciplinary committee book, and announcement book.

In this regard, records management is the area of management concerned with achieving accuracy, efficiency, and economy in the systematic creation, retention, conservation, dissemination, use, and disposition of the official records of a business, government agency, organization, or institution, whether in physical form or electronic form. Management of statutory records in academic department is herculean task for university administrator. In general, record keeping must adhere to certain confidentiality requirements, proper upkeep, security, preservation of the information and context, and other considerations. Academic Heads of Department productivity in the context of university systems is typically determined by the degree to which academic heads contribute to achieving the organization's goals of teaching and research activities, which could be measured on staff development, student's performance and accreditation of courses.

Methodology

This study adopted correlation design. The target population comprised of all 400 Academic Heads of Department in the public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. These include: University of Lagos (UNILAG), Lagos State University (LASU), Lagos State University of Education (LASUED) and Lagos State University of Science and Technology (LASUST). The sample size comprised 120 Heads of Department randomly selected for the study. An instrument titled: 'Records Management Practices Questionnaire' (RMPQ) and 'Academic Heads of Department Questionnaire' (AHDQ) were used for data collection. The questionnaire was purposively administered to 150 academic Heads of Department in all Faculties in the three public universities owned by Lagos State. 30 academic Heads of Department were randomly selected from all faculties in public universities under study through simple random sampling techniques. The structured questionnaire was developed and divided into two sections: Section A and B. Section A contains the personal information of the respondents and section B contains 20 items focus on the research questions. Each statement is measured on a four-point modifier Likert-type-rating scale, namely: "Strongly Agree (SA)", "Agree (A)", "Disagree (D)" and "Strongly Disagree (SD)". The data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient. The content validity of the instruments was ensured by test experts and the reliability index of the instrument was persistently determined through Cronbach's alpha at 0.67 and 0.65 meaning that the instrument was reliable.

Results and Discussion

Test of Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between monitoring of staff records and productivity of academic Head of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Pearson’s correlation analysis between monitoring of staff records and productivity of academic Head of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Variables		Monitoring of Staff Records	Productivity of Academic Head of Department
Monitoring of Staff Records	Pearson Correlation	1	.631**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	120	120
Productivity of Academic Head of Department	Pearson Correlation	.631**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	120	120

* Correlation is significant at $p < 0.05$ level (2-tailed)

Table 1 indicates that there is a positive significant relationship between monitoring of staff records and productivity of academic Head of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria ($r = .631$; $N=120$; $p < 0.05$, 2-tailed). This means that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between monitoring of staff records and productivity of academic Head of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria is rejected since $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between monitoring of staff records and productivity of academic Head of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. This finding is in line with Garry and Dave (2021) that record keeping with the computer captures and retains digital information on electromagnetic, optical or silicon-based recording keeping media for future use which invariably would enhance school administrators’ effectiveness.

Test of Hypothesis Two

There is no significant relationship between. controlling of student records and productivity of academic heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria

Table 2: Pearson’s correlation analysis between controlling of student records and productivity of academic Heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Variables		Controlling of Student Records	Productivity of Academic Heads of Department
Controlling of Student Records	Pearson Correlation	1	.631**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	120	120
Productivity of Academic Heads of Department	Pearson Correlation	.631**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	120	120

* Correlation is significant at $p < 0.05$ level (2-tailed)

Table 1 indicates that there is a positive significant relationship between controlling of student records and productivity of academic heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria ($r = .631$; $N=120$; $p < 0.05$, 2-tailed). This means that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between controlling of student records and productivity of academic heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria is rejected since $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between controlling of student records and productivity of academic heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The findings of this study corroborated with the findings of researchers like Coetzer (2012), Chinyemba and Ngulube (2005) who argued that the management of university records has not been effective and efficient. This includes lack of knowledge of existing legislations in place relating to records keeping in public institutions for instance in terms of access to information, and desirable controls at each stage of the records life cycle.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concluded that monitoring and controlling of statutory records enhanced the productivity of academic Heads of Department in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The creation of policies and adherence to university management programs may be influenced by records. By allowing for the efficient, transparent, accountable, and organized management of university documents, it may also help to improve service delivery. The essence of record keeping is to enable the heads of Department to make effective decision and formulate relevant policies. Some of these records kept are: number of lecturers recruited, non-teaching staff, students' personal files, the school calendar, staff minutes book, visitors' book and so on.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. University management should direct all Deans, Directors, Heads of Department to plan, monitor and control statutory records of both staff and students which will enhance their productivity.
2. University policy makers should initiate records management practice that could help Administrator to manage their information effectively, efficiently, fulfill their mandate, protect them from litigation, foster accountability and good administration.
3. Seminars, training and workshops on record management practice should be organized by the university management for all academic Head of Department in order improve their efficiency.
4. Government should provide adequate fund and supply the necessary electronic and digital record keeping devices such as internet, maintenance of ICT facilities, computers and their accessories to all Heads of Department in public universities.

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